

Virtual On-board Unit Migration in a Multi-access Smart-Campus 5G Architecture

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Abstract—By embracing the next generation of network architectures, academic institutions are setting the scene to expand the research capabilities, enhance the learning experience of the students, and showcase how smart-city-like solutions can transform traditional educational environments into innovative platforms with state-of-the-art solutions. In this work, we present the University of Murcia’s GAIA 5G multi-access smart-campus architecture as an enabler for research and experimentation in novel use cases related to Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) scenarios. In this way, we demonstrate how a vehicular service that provides digital twins for on-board units with migration capabilities between virtualization domains has been integrated in an operational 5G environment. The experimental tests demonstrates the validity of the solution, which can be seamlessly deployed and operated in a real 5G network.

Index Terms—5G, CAM, NEF

I. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of 5G infrastructures in university campuses brings several advantages in both education and research aspects. Ultra-fast data transfer speeds, huge network capacity, ultra-low latencies, or reliable connections are some of the benefits that 5G-powered campus networks are experiencing. With an strategy focused on improving the Quality of Experience (QoE) of the users, academic institutions can create smarter and more efficient learning environments to address the digital needs of future generations. Furthermore, the adoption of the technologies that lay the foundations of 5G architectures, permits the transformation of smart-campus in small smart-cities. By doing so, rich and heterogeneous environments can be created to enhance the multidisciplinary research among faculties and research centers within the institution. This 5G-enabled campuses seamlessly integrate a variety of applications and capabilities that foster innovation, collaboration, and creativity.

In this line, as already presented in [1], the University of Murcia (Spain) has deployed a multi-access 5G smart-campus infrastructure: GAIA 5G. It provides a private 5G infrastructure composed by four 5G independent, but interoperable, networks as cornerstones of the communication architecture.

Furthermore, it provides LoRaWAN access points for Internet of Things (IoT) communications, and PC5/G5 infrastructure is being installed to enable vehicular services through these interfaces. Fig. 1 depicts the current status of the deployment. The infrastructure offers virtualization and cloud capabilities through Software Defined Networking (SDN), Network Function Virtualization (NFV) and Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC). Currently, GAIA 5G is being employed as a state-of-the-art 5G testbed in multiple European projects such as 5GASP, or NANCY, and in multiple national projects such as CERBERUS, CRETA, or R3CAV, among others.

GAIA 5G infrastructure is one of the testbeds participating in the 5GASP project [2]. The aim of 5GASP is to ease the development and validation of 5G network applications by offering an infrastructure composed by different testbeds following a “ready-to-use” model. Concretely, GAIA 5G is the testbed responsible for Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) vertical applications, in collaboration with Odin Solutions (a private company). Odin Solutions is developing a 5G network application that permits the creation of virtual twins of the physical On-Board Units (OBUs) located in the vehicles [3], an idea that was first presented in the 5G-INFIRE project [4]. This digital twin acts as a replica of the OBU located at the MEC layer, serving as an intermediate cache and reducing the latency to access vehicle data [5]. Furthermore, the virtual OBU (vOBU) can follow the vehicle across different MEC domains to improve the performance of the system and maintain an optimal data access time [6]. Thanks to the participation of Odin Solutions in the 5GASP project, this solution is being transformed in a functional 5G network application.

The aim of this work is to showcase the use of the GAIA 5G smart-campus architecture as an enabler for research and experimentation in innovative use cases, concretely, related to CAM scenarios. Therefore, the contribution of this work is to describe how the GAIA 5G infrastructure has been used to demonstrate the operation of 5G network applications within the context of the 5GASP project.

Fig. 1. University of Murcia’s GAIA 5G architecture.

The rest of the document is organized as follows. Section II explores existing proposals of smart-campuses to empower research and education. The use case is presented in Section III together with the specific infrastructure modifications that have been performed. Section IV showcase how the GAIA 5G smart-campus architecture has been used to demonstrate the operation of the 5G network application. And, finally, the conclusions and future research lines are discussed in Section V.

II. BACKGROUND

The adoption of state-of-the-art technologies in smart-campuses is creating environments that foster the innovation in academic communities, helping the development of new ideas on top of this infrastructures. Work in [7] highlighted the importance of the 5G campus networks innovations as key enablers for the next generation of mobile communications: 6G. Authors stated that the deployment of open campus networks and open end-to-end 5G testbeds is of utmost importance for research and for the development of new services and use cases. Besides, they also envision that the evolution of this kind of networks will be driven by the integration of non-terrestrial networks and a deeper integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies for network orchestration and management. In [8], the authors presented a framework that leverages 5G, AI and cloud computing technologies in campus networks as enablers for smart-cities. The framework is designed to support the research in many use cases and industry verticals, considering AI as the key technology to further expand the capabilities of this kind of networks. Work in [9] discussed the importance of the combination of 5G and AI to build smart-campuses. Besides, it proposed the creation of a “cloud-network-edge-service” architecture to provide a better service to students, professors and researchers. This model has the

advantages of providing personalized services thanks to the integration and intelligent analysis of the campus-data, which can also feed research lines with a living campus community.

Therefore, the main objective of this work is to present how a multi-access smart-campus 5G infrastructure, namely, GAIA 5G, can serve as a demonstrator for novel technologies and services. The environment in this kind of networks is very similar to real-world large-scale commercial deployments, thus they are ideal to be used as testbeds to validate the development of new solutions prior to their deployment in production environments.

III. USE CASE

As previously introduced, GAIA 5G is being used as a demonstrator testbed for CAM scenarios in the context of the 5GASP European project in a collaboration between the University of Murcia and Odin Solutions. The 5GASP project aims at reducing the idea-to-market process by creating an European network of testbeds for Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs) to foster the development and validation of innovative 5G network applications using their reference architecture. GAIA 5G is integrated within this ecosystem and it provides the developers with the necessary tools to test their 5G network applications in a real-world 5G network, without requiring any further knowledge from the underlying infrastructure. In this environment, the exhibited use case was the deployment of the vOBU 5G network application and its validation following a real OBU in a vehicle by automatically migrating between two different MEC domains. The insights of the use case are detailed in the following.

The majority of modern vehicles driving around the world are equipped with physical OBUs following a client-server approach, in which the OBU gathers the vehicle data directly from the sensors and sends it to the cloud. This model is

becoming outdated with the new capabilities that the next generation of communication networks are bringing. Thanks to the MEC paradigm, intermediate nodes located between the client and the cloud with high caching and computing performance can be used as an intermediate layer between the OBUs and the cloud services. The main objective of the vOBU 5G network application is to act as a digital twin of the physical OBU in the MEC layer and enable quasi-ubiquitous data-gathering and offloading of the vehicular sensors data. Besides, this solution has the capabilities to follow the vehicle among different virtualization domains, maintaining an optimal level of data access latency. By following this approach, the services making use of the information gathered in the vehicles can operate with an increased robustness and performance, as it helps to avoid the characteristics disconnections suffered in vehicular environments.

Fig. 2 depicts the general architecture of the vOBU 5G network application. As it can be seen, it comprises four components: (i) the OBU is the physical device installed in the vehicle and directly connected to the sensors; (ii) the vOBU located in the MEC, which acts as a digital twin of the physical OBU; (iii) the vOBU manager, located in the cloud and in charge of the control and orchestration of the vOBUs, and (iv) the aggregator, which is the main database of the system and acts as a single point of entry to the service. Whenever an external client desires to access to the vehicle data, its query will arrive through the aggregator, which tries to maintain an up-to-date copy of the information from the vehicle sensors. In case the data is not present, the query will be forwarded to the vOBU, which maintains the newest copy of this desired information, and can serve it as well. In the worst case scenario, the queried data will have to be retrieved directly from the vehicle. Besides, the vOBU 5G network application will track the location of the vehicle monitoring the status of the 5G network and the cell that is currently serving it. Whenever the vehicle moves to a location, i.e., connects to another cell closer to another virtualization domain, a migration process will be triggered. In this procedure, a copy of the vOBU currently serving the vehicle is instantiated in the new MEC domain and, once ready, it is assigned to serve the vehicle instead of the old vOBU, which is terminated.

In order to integrate a network application into the 5G infrastructure, the application has to interact in some way with the 5G network. That is the reason why the vOBU solution was selected in the 5GASP project to evolve towards a 5G network application. Originally, the solution relied on the interaction with the SDN controller of each segment of the architecture, which was heavily coupled with the underlying infrastructure and required insight knowledge of the network. During the development of the 5GASP project, a new approach was designed and implemented. The 5G core specification [10] implements the Network Exposure Function (NEF) [11], which is defined as the interaction point of the 5G core to which the applications can query monitoring and performance data of the network operation. Among all the network information exposed, the NEF offers the cell that is serving the client

in each moment, therefore, this data can be used to trigger the migrations proposed by the vOBU solution.

However, to the author's knowledge, there is no implementations of the NEF neither in open source 5G core solutions nor in commercial deployments. In consequence, it was necessary to find a workaround. In this point is where the 5GASP project tools [12] help the developers to validate their 5G network application in testbeds with real-world equivalent characteristics. The 5GASP project consortium, conscious of the issues raised with the NEF availability, prepared and deployed an instance of the NEF Emulator [13] developed in the European project EVOLVED-5G [14]. This emulator enables the interaction of the 5G network applications with an emulated NEF that behaves exactly as if it was a real NEF part of the 5G core. In this way, it is possible to continue the development of the 5G interaction functions as if a real one was available.

Consequently, the vOBU 5G network application was enhanced to interact with the NEF Emulator. In the emulator, a 5G network similar to the one offered by GAIA 5G is configured, and a client is defined to follow a path between two different cells, enabling the emulation of a handover between cells (see Fig. 3). Thanks to this interaction, it is possible to validate the operation of the vOBU 5G network application in a real 5G infrastructure with the same interactions that would occur with a real NEF.

Finally, besides the development and validation framework offered by the 5GASP project, the GAIA 5G testbed also offers additional capabilities such as 5G network monitoring through specific developed software. Thanks to the exposure of these 5G network metrics, the cell to which each OBU is connected is available to be retrieved by the applications running in the infrastructure. Therefore, the vOBU 5G network application, with no further modifications, is capable of operate in the same way as it does with the NEF emulator in the controlled 5GASP environment. This showcases the usefulness of the 5GASP framework, as a 5G solution developed and validated in the 5GASP testbed can be directly deployed in a real 5G network and operate in a safe and correct way.

IV. DEMONSTRATION

As aforementioned, the demonstration was divided in two parts. In the first one, the vOBU 5G network application was evaluated within the 5GASP framework, being executed in a controlled indoor lab environment with only one cell and interacting with the NEF emulator to track the vehicle location and trigger the migration with that emulated data. In the second one, the same exact software was deployed in the outdoor 5G network on a moving vehicle, triggering the migration process by effectively switching 5G cells. The insights of the underlying 5G and virtualization infrastructure and the demonstration details are presented below.

GAIA 5G infrastructure currently counts with four different and interoperable 5G networks, two of them were used in the demonstration. The indoor lab equipment for the first part described above was an Amarisoft Callbox, with three 2x2 full

Fig. 2. vOBU 5G network application architecture.

Fig. 3. NEF Emulator GUI.

duplex SDR elements. The outdoor one was a 5G Stand Alone (SA) network based on a fully functional solution provided by Amarisoft [15]. This network uses two macro cells composed of their respective Remote Radio Heads (RRHs) and connected to a gNB implementing Amarisoft software. Each RRH provide 20 MHz on the n78 band with a 2x2 MIMO configuration and 20 W of power. Intra-frequency handover parameters were fine tuned to achieve zero connectivity loss in the transition zone between cells by adjusting the UE measurement reports and handover trigger with RSRP measurements from various test runs done with a Keysight NEMO Handy [16] tool and an Anritsu FieldMaster MS2090A [17]. The OBUs are based on Globalscale tech.'s "Mochabin" [18] embedded appliances that are powered by a quad core ARM A72 Marvell Armada and 4GB of DDR4 RAM that we complemented with Quectel RM520N-GL 5G R16 modems, an Atheros 9k WiFi chipset

Fig. 4. 5G OBUs mounted in the vehicle used for the demonstration.

with driver modifications for 802.11p communication modes and a custom Debian-based software stack. The used antennae are the Quectel YB0007 integrated antenna [19], that embeds four 5G multi-band antenna that enables full 2x2 MIMO, and a GPS receiver. To enable the demonstration in a CAM scenario, a Seat Ibiza 2007 car was prepared with the 5G OBU mounted in the top of the trunk and with the antennas attached to the roof of the car, as it can be seen in Fig. 4; note that we deployed two OBUs to achieve redundancy, but only one was used for the demonstration. To complete the deployment, a power regulator, a fuse box, and a secondary battery was installed in the setup.

Regarding the computation and virtualization infrastructure, Openstack was the virtual infrastructure manager used, with two compute nodes based on Rocky version, one per MEC domain and each one located near each one of the used gNBs. They were interconnected with the 5G network through a 40 Gbps link between buildings, which also connects them to the 5G network. Besides, to manage and orchestrate the dynamic deployment of the vOBU 5G Network Application,

Fig. 5. Dynamic OBU connectivity with active cells.

Fig. 6. Cell change detection and instantiation of the new vOBU.

Open Source MANO (OSM) was the chosen orchestrator.

Once the infrastructure was prepared, the vOBU network application was onboarded, deployed and validated. The followed steps were the same as the ones already described in our previous work [5], where we showcase how it is possible to deploy and test a 5G network application within the 5GASP framework. After completing this stage, the application is running and ready for the demonstration.

In the first part of the experiments, as previously explained, the OBU was located in an indoor lab connected to the Amarisoft Callbox 5G solution. Through this network, it had access to the 5GASP NEF Emulator instance deployed for the developers. In this way, the OBU could authenticate and subscribe to cell change events in the NEF Emulator. To do so, the application had to attach itself to a previously generated path that travelled between two emulated cells (see Fig. 3). Whenever the simulated device changed from one coverage area to another, the event is generated and the vOBU 5G network application was able to migrate the vOBU instance from one MEC domain to another one.

To showcase how the 5GASP project provides a framework to develop and validate 5G network applications in realistic scenarios, the part two of the demonstration used the same vOBU 5G network application instance deployed in the first part. The only difference was that the client OBU software was running in a OBU located in a real moving vehicle, connected to the outdoor 5G network. This OBU can be seen in Fig. 4.

The path followed by the vehicle in the University of Murcia campus during the demonstration is shown in Fig. 5, where the blue points indicate that the OBU was connected to the first cell, whose Physical Cell ID (PCI) was 501, and the brown ones represent the connection to the second cell (PCI 502). Also, each cell had an adjacent associated MEC domain where the vOBUs were instantiated. The car started its route near the first cell, to ensure a good coverage at the start of the trial. Then, it traveled at a maximum speed of 30 km/h towards the coverage area of the second cell. Note in Fig. 5 how the color changed when the OBU made the handover between the two cells. The triggering of the new vOBU instantiation in the second MEC domain can be seen in Fig. 6. The top graph shows the PCIs to which the OBUs were connected during the experiment. The OBUs 1 and 2 were used in the first part of the demonstration, hence they were connected to the indoor cell with PCI 500. The OBUs 3 and 4 were the ones onboarded in the car, being the number 4 the one running the application. Below, the CPU usage of the Openstack compute node, so-called, “Aguiles”, located in the second MEC domain is depicted. It can be seen how the PCI change (from 501 to 502) due to the handover displayed in Fig. 5, which triggered a considerable increment of the CPU usage in the second virtualization domain. This behaviour is because the vOBU 5G network application detected the cell change and initiated the migration process from the MEC closest to the cell with PCI 501, to the site adjacent to the second cell. Hence, the deployment of the new vOBU increased the CPU usage in the second MEC domain. Once the instantiation was finished, the migrated vOBU was assigned to the OBU and the system continued its normal operation.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Smart-campus are gaining relevance during the last years, as they enable the creation of innovative and creative spaces that can foster both the education and the research performed in academic institutions. These environments empower the multidisciplinary research among centres and serve as a platform to demonstrate the usefulness of novel technologies, such as in the case of GAIA 5G. It is a multi-access smart-campus infrastructure deployed in the University of Murcia (Spain), which provides a private 5G infrastructure, IoT communications and CAM services. GAIA 5G is participating as a testbed in the European project 5GASP, which aims at easing the development and validation of 5G network applications. In this work, we have showed how the GAIA 5G infrastructure is an enabler for research and experimentation in a wide variety of verticals, such as CAM. Besides, we have detailed how this architecture has been used in the context of the 5GASP project to demonstrate the usefulness of the tools provided by the project to easily develop and validate 5G network applications in controlled environments. GAIA 5G will continue to evolve with the aim of supporting new use cases and integrate novel technologies, enabling the design, development, deployment and validation of new applications and services.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. Gallego-Madrid, L. Bernal-Escobedo, R. Asensio, A. Hermosilla, A. M. Zarca, J. Ortiz, R. Sanchez-Iborra, and A. Skarmeta, "GAIA 5G: A Multi-access Smart-Campus Architecture," in *Internet of Things*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, A. González-Vidal, A. Mohamed Abdelgawad, E. Sabir, S. Ziegler, and L. Ladid, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022, pp. 363–374.
- [2] "5GASP," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://5gasp.eu/>
- [3] J. Santa, P. J. Fernández, J. Ortiz, R. Sanchez-Iborra, and A. F. Skarmeta, "SURROGATES: Virtual OBUs to Foster 5G Vehicular Services," *Electronics*, vol. 8, no. 2, p. 117, Feb. 2019, number: 2 Publisher: Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/8/2/117>
- [4] "5GinFIRE," Dec. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://5ginfire.eu/>
- [5] J. Gallego-Madrid, A. Hermosilla, and A. F. Skarmeta, "Dynamic Deployment and Testing of Virtual On-board Units in 5G," in *2022 IEEE Future Networks World Forum (FNWF)*, Oct. 2022, pp. 305–309, iSSN: 2770-7679.
- [6] J. Santa, J. Ortiz, P. J. Fernandez, M. Luis, C. Gomes, J. Oliveira, D. Gomes, R. Sanchez-Iborra, S. Sargento, and A. F. Skarmeta, "MIGRATE: Mobile Device Virtualisation Through State Transfer," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 25 848–25 862, 2020, conference Name: IEEE Access.
- [7] M. Emmelmann, M. Corici, F. Eichhorn, M. Hauswirth, and T. Magedanz, "Open 5G campus networks: key drivers for 6G innovations," *e & i Elektrotechnik und Informationstechnik*, vol. 139, no. 7, pp. 589–600, Nov. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00502-022-01064-7>
- [8] R. Mohamed and S. Zemouri, "Towards a Cloud-Native 5G Service Chaining for IoT and Video Analytics in Smart Campus," in *2022 5th Conference on Cloud and Internet of Things (CIoT)*, Mar. 2022, pp. 186–188.
- [9] Y. Wei, "Research on the Construction of "Cloud-network-edge-device" Integrated Campus Intelligent System Based on 5G+AI," in *2022 Fourth International Conference on Emerging Research in Electronics, Computer Science and Technology (ICERECT)*, Dec. 2022, pp. 1–6.
- [10] "Specification # 23.501." [Online]. Available: <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3144>
- [11] "Specification # 29.591." [Online]. Available: <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3681>
- [12] "5GASP H2020 Project Git," <https://github.com/5gasp>.
- [13] "Medianetlab/NEF_emulator: Configurable, emulated environment for providing Network Exposure Function (NEF) APIs," https://github.com/medianetlab/NEF_emulator.
- [14] "Home." [Online]. Available: <https://evolved-5g.eu>
- [15] "Amarisoft Software," <https://www.amarisoft.com/>.
- [16] Keysight, "Nemo Handy Handheld Measurement Solution," <https://www.keysight.com/es/en/product/NTH50047B/nemo-handy-handheld-measurement-solution.html>.
- [17] "Field Master Pro MS2090A — Anritsu America," <https://www.anritsu.com/en-us/test-measurement/products/ms2090a>.
- [18] "About MOCHAbin," http://espressobin.net/mochabin_wiki/tiki-index.php?page=About+MOCHAbin.
- [19] "YB0007AA 5G Screw Mount Combo Antenna Box," <https://www.quectel.com/product/yb0007aa-5g-screw-mount-combo-antenna-box>.